

IMPROVEMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND LEGAL BASES OF FOREIGN ECONOMIC ACTIVITY

J.G. Saidmusayev

Sarboon University, Department of Legal Sciences, Senior Lecturer

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19216769>

***Abstract.** Protection of the domestic market is one of the most important areas of the state's influence on the economy. Along with the defense capability of Uzbekistan, it is important to have the competitiveness of goods. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to create a strong industrial base in the country, create a legal infrastructure, establish strong legal relations with the economy of foreign countries, and protect productive sectors of industry from unfair competition of foreign companies. One of such protective measures is measures to protect the internal market of goods in the implementation of foreign economic activity. In this mechanism, anti-dumping, compensation and special protection measures introduced by the government of Uzbekistan play a key role.*

***Keywords:** currency control, tax control, customs control, dumping, anti-dumping and regulation.*

Introduction

In the general sense, the legal mechanism in this area is, first of all, a set of management tools by which scientifically based management decisions are made and their effective implementation is achieved. The essence of the mechanism is that it combines the main elements of management and acts as an organizational tool, a single management tool for making and implementing management decisions. Consequently, the administrative and legal regulation of foreign economic activity proceeds from the creation and provision of conditions for society to operate on the basis of current regulatory and legal documents. The basis for the implementation of these processes is the changes taking place in Uzbekistan, which attempts to comprehensively study the state and development of administrative and legal regulation of foreign economic activity in Uzbekistan using the example of the main elements of this activity. The relevance of the research is also determined by the fact that the system of state regulation of foreign economic activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan is currently being improved.

The need to improve the organizational legal framework is due to the fact that many issues of applying measures to protect the domestic market in this activity are not regulated by the relevant legal relations. Effective national legislation in the field of applying measures to protect the domestic market of goods in the implementation of state management of foreign economic activity, if studied and applied only in the part that corresponds to the interests of the domestic economy, will create mechanisms for protecting the domestic market with specific national characteristics. Currently, it is possible to take measures to protect the domestic market in the implementation of foreign economic activity by implementing restrictive measures to protect the domestic market of goods.

The application of measures to protect the domestic market in the implementation of foreign economic activity has international legal, constitutional legal, administrative legal, financial legal and economic legal aspects. In order to prevent the one-sidedness of the legal

sphere, it is necessary to combine the efforts of many legal scholars in the study of such a law institute. Their dissertations should begin with an understanding of the legal essence of the above-mentioned measures and the principles of their application. At the same time, it is impossible not to take into account the approach developed over the years in the analysis of the administrative activity of the state in implementing market protection, since the activities of the executive authorities in this area have a clearly administrative nature.

Measures to protect the domestic market in the implementation of foreign economic activity are also a source of negotiation for the foreign trade policy of Uzbekistan. The state plays a special role in the development of foreign economic activity. It is precisely high-quality management of foreign economic activity that allows us to achieve the main goal of modern regulation of Uzbekistan's foreign economic activity - its integration into the world economy. Effective integration is based on such management.

In the Decree No. PF-158 dated September 11, 2023 on the STRATEGY “Uzbekistan - 2030”, our President Sh. Mirziyoyev also stated that foreign economic activity should be considered as part of the state's foreign policy, as well as the national economic policy, therefore it should be regulated by the state, and the mechanism of legal regulation of foreign economic activity, primarily the use of various legal instruments that perform specific functions in the system of legal regulation of foreign economic relations, should be brought to new levels as the main task. Protectionist measures are aimed at directly restricting exports and imports in order to protect certain national industries, for example, quotas and licensing, export controls, and import safeguards. Administrative measures restrict foreign economic activity by setting technical, sanitary, and environmental standards for imported goods, and price preferences are eliminated.

Currently, states are developing a system of administrative and legal regulation of foreign economic activity. In general, there are about a hundred state intervention measures in the world. In general, they can be divided into the following groups:

1. Economic measures:

- export and production subsidies;
- anti-dumping duties;
- import deposits;
- exchange rate regulation;
- export and import taxes, excise duties;
- compulsory sale of part of foreign currency earnings;
- system of state orders;
- financing of research;
- nationalization/privatization of property.

2. Technical measures:

- requirements for compliance with national standards;
- quality acceptance, certification;
- sanitary and environmental standards;
- safety standards.

3. Administrative regulatory measures:

- customs tariffs;
- currency control;
- declaration of goods;
- embargo;

- quotas, quotas;
- licenses;
- directive setting of contract prices;
- restrictions on types of foreign trade operations.

Foreign economic activity is understood as a separate specific type of activity of economic entities. Each enterprise carries out this activity independently, based on the choice of a foreign market. This is foreign trade, investment and other activities in the field of international exchange of goods, information, works, services, results of intellectual activity, rights to the results of intellectual activity. This activity also includes production cooperation in these areas. Legal regulation of foreign economic activity in Uzbekistan and in other countries is based on the state monopoly of foreign trade. Foreign economic activity is reflected in international and our state practice in various forms and types. Foreign experience identifies the following types of foreign economic activity:

- foreign trade activity;
- production cooperation;
- currency and financial and credit operations;
- relations with international organizations.

Foreign trade activity is one of the most widespread areas of foreign economic activity. Transactions on such activities are formalized by foreign trade agreements. Agreements are divided into import-export, leasing, investment, financial and other types. Foreign economic activity contracts are concluded in foreign currency and are carried out in accordance with international rules. The following forms of foreign trade activity are distinguished: a) export transactions; b) import transactions; c) barter transactions.

Research methodology

Foreign trade is one of the most widespread areas of foreign economic activity. Transactions on such activities are formalized by foreign trade agreements. Agreements are divided into import-export, leasing, investment, financial and other types. Contracts on foreign economic activity are concluded in foreign currency and are carried out in accordance with international rules. The following forms of foreign trade activity are distinguished: a) export transactions; b) import transactions; c) barter transactions. In most sources discussing foreign economic activity, this area of social relations operate as a subsystem of the economy. As a result, economic concepts form the basis of the concepts used in foreign economic activity. Therefore, not only the definition of “foreign economic activity” is often used, but the general definition is “foreign economic sphere”.

At the same time, when it comes to the foreign economic sphere, a very wide range of concepts is used. Each of them has a certain status, which depends on the place occupied by this concept in the subsystem under consideration. The following concepts are basic and occupy a special place in the field of foreign economic activity: foreign economic activity, foreign trade activity, foreign economic relations. It is very important that these concepts are not differentiated in modern legislation, but are hierarchically interconnected, while not losing their main ability - the property of being integral. Foreign economic activity includes such processes as the exchange of goods and services between states, the movement of capital and labor, the spread of technologies and knowledge. At the same time, foreign economic activity depends not only on economic changes, but also on political, social and environmental factors. States use various legal forms to regulate foreign economic activity in implementing their economic policy.

Analysis and results. Currency legislation for regulating foreign economic activity includes a number of legal mechanisms, norms and standards. Through these mechanisms, states manage trade and investment activities. Ensuring exchange rate stability is one of the most important tasks of currency legislation. Strong fluctuations in the national exchange rate can complicate foreign economic activity and disrupt trade relations. Therefore, states manage foreign trade and investment by managing the exchange rate. Some countries freely determine the exchange rate of their national currency based on market supply and demand. Through such a system, the exchange rate adapts to the state of the national economy. Some countries stabilize it by intervening against sharp fluctuations in the exchange rate. This is usually done by central banks and is done in order to support the market. Capital movement management is another important task carried out through currency legislation. States try to maintain the stability of the national economy by controlling capital flows.

Capital outflow and inflow: Some countries regulate the outflow of capital abroad or the inflow of capital from abroad with restrictions. This is mainly aimed at ensuring economic stability and maintaining foreign exchange reserves. Through currency legislation, countries can provide tax breaks and other incentives to attract foreign investment. This, in turn, ensures economic growth and job creation. Through currency exchange management, countries try to protect the domestic market and normalize foreign economic relations. Currency legislation is mainly aimed at controlling and regulating transactions carried out in the foreign exchange market. **Restrictions on foreign exchange transactions:** Some countries may regulate foreign exchange transactions with special restrictions. For example, licenses may be required to buy or sell certain currencies. **Foreign exchange reports:** Companies and organizations engaged in foreign economic activities may be required to submit special calculations.

Through this, countries have the opportunity to verify the correctness of international trade transactions. Currency law provides countries with international mechanisms for regulating international trade and investment. Through this, economic relations between countries are coordinated and standardized. Currency transactions and capital movements are governed by trade agreements and investment treaties concluded between countries. For example, international organizations such as the United Nations (UN) and the World Trade Organization (WTO) set standards related to currency law. **International currency agreements:** International agreements are concluded to coordinate currency exchange and capital flows between countries. These agreements are mainly implemented to manage exchange rates, encourage foreign investment, and regulate international financial systems. Currency law serves as an important tool in regulating foreign economic activity. It creates the necessary legal mechanisms to manage countries' foreign trade, capital flows, and exchange rate operations.

Through currency legislation, states help ensure their economic security, coordinate their international economic relations and maintain economic stability, and the existing legislation has only created a new basis for the development and restructuring of currency regulation and currency control. However, it is impossible to implement it without a deeper study of the theoretical foundations of legal regulation of currency relations, based on domestic and foreign experience. It is necessary to establish alternative and relatively clear sanctions that allow individualizing financial responsibility, and financial sanctions should be regulated not only at the level of departmental regulatory documents, but also at the level of laws. All this will allow the Republic of Uzbekistan to become a full member of the international economic community.

Conclusions and recommendations. Laws and regulations regulating foreign economic activity in administrative management are important for ensuring the country's economic security, attracting foreign investment and developing foreign trade.

Regulatory mechanisms: Updating and strengthening the rules regulating foreign economic activity. This increases the state's ability to manage all processes related to foreign economic activity.

Openness and transparency: Publicly disclosing information on foreign trade operations and agreements. This improves the business environment and increases investor confidence.

Analysis and monitoring: Introducing special monitoring systems to monitor and analyze foreign economic activity. This allows for timely identification of negative trends.

Personnel training: Training qualified personnel in the field of foreign economic activity and updating their knowledge. This helps to improve control and management processes.

Investment support: Creating special programs and incentives to attract foreign investment. This makes it easier for foreign companies to enter our country.

Constantly updating and adapting the legislation on foreign economic activity to modern requirements and standards. It is necessary to strengthen cooperation with international economic organizations and other countries, exchange experiences, and jointly develop new regulatory mechanisms.

REFERENCES

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan // National database of legislative documents, dated 30.04.2023, No. 03/21/671/0093.
2. “Customs Code” of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 02.02.2022 // National database of legislative documents, dated 02.02.2022, No. 03/22/748/0086.
3. “Tax Code” of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 06.05.2022 // National database of legislative documents, dated 06.05.2022, No. 03/22/767/0386.
4. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 14.03.2022 “On Competition” //National database of legal documents information 14.03.2022., No. 03/22/759/0213.
5. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 21.04.2021 “On Foreign Economic Activity” //National database of legal documents information 21.04.2021., No. 03/21/683/0375.
6. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 07.02.2019 “On International Treaties” //National database of legal documents information 07.02.2019., No. 03/19/518/2589.